

Strongly-Typed Geometric Syntactic Genetic Programming

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1 Experimental Setup Function and Terminal Type Tables

Table 7: Functions Types Table Symbolic Regression

Function	arity	arg types	return type
add	2	float, float	float
sub	2	float, float	float
mult	2	float, float	float
div	2	float, float	float
sin	1	float	float
cos	1	float	float
exp	1	float	float
lnmod	1	float	float

Table 8: Terminal Types Table Symbolic Regression

Terminal	Data type
x_1, \dots, x_n	float
Ephemeral constant	float

Table 9: Function Types Table N-Multiplexer

Function	Arity	Arg types	Return
if-then-else	3	bool, bool, bool	bool
and	2	bool, bool	bool
or	2	bool, bool	bool
not	1	bool	bool

Table 10: Terminal Types Table N-Multiplexer

Function	data type
$(bit_1 \dots, bit_N)$	bool

Table 11: Function Types Table Lunar Lander

Function	Arity	Arg types	Return
if-then-else-action	3	bool action action action	action
if-then-else	3	bool float float	float
add	2	float float	float
sub	2	float float	float
mult	2	float float	float
div	2	float float	float
eq	2	float float	bool
lt	2	float float	bool
gt	2	float float	bool
cos	1	float	float
sin	1	float	float
tan	1	float	float
and	2	bool bool	bool
or	2	bool bool	bool
not	1	bool	bool

Table 12: Terminal Types Table Lunar Lander

Terminal	data type
x-cord	float
y-cord	float
x-velocity	float
y-velocity	float
angle	float
angular-velocity	float
left-leg-contact	bool
right-leg-contact	bool
uniform-constant	float
nothing	action
fire-action	action
left-action	action
right-action	action